

Condensation of Azeloyl chloride and Sebasoyl chloride with Phenols and Phenolic Ethers

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Azeloyl chloride and sebasoyl chloride have, on condensation with phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols and their methyl ethers in the presence of aluminium chloride, led to the formation of 1,9-diketones and 8-keto acids and 1,10-diketones and 9-keto acids respectively.

In earlier papers Chakravarti and coworkers^{1,2,3} have described the condensation of glutaryl chloride, adipyl chloride, pimelyl chloride and suberyl chloride with free phenols in the presence of aluminium chloride in a suitable solvent e.g., nitrobenzene.

In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of azeloyl chloride and sebasoyl chloride with phenols and phenolic ethers. In the case of azeloyl chloride and sebasoyl chloride, *p*-substituted phenols yield *o*-hydroxy diketones and keto-acids. The condensation of *p*-chlorophenol with azeloyl and sebasoyl chloride yields only keto acids and the diketones are not obtained.

Phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols and their methyl ethers condense with azeloyl and sebasoyl chloride forming 1,9 and 1,10-diketone (I) and 8- and 9-keto acids (II) respectively.

1. *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 607.
2. *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 33.
3. *This Journal*, 1969, **46**, 351

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of azeloyl chloride ClCO-(CH₂)₇-COCl and sebasoyl chloride ClCO-(CH₂)₈-COCl: Azeloyl chloride (b.p. 150°/5 mm) and sebasoyl chloride (b.p. 155°/5 mm) are obtained from *dry* azelaic acid and dry sebasic acid by treatment with thionyl chloride in the usual manner.

1,9-bis (*p*-hydroxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9-dione (I, R₂ = OH; R = R₁ = R₃ = R₄ = H; n = 7).

A solution of freshly distilled phenol (2 g.) in nitrobenzene (30 ml.) was taken in a 250 ml. three-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a CaCl₂ guard tube. Aluminium chloride (4 g.) was added to the solution maintained at 0°–5°. A solution of azeloyl chloride (2.3 g.) in nitrobenzene (10 ml.) was added through the dropping funnel over a period of 1 hr. The stirring was continued for a further period of 4 hrs, at room temperature. The product was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and distilled with steam to remove excess of nitrobenzene. The crude product solidified on cooling for about 12 hrs. It was insoluble in NaHCO₃ solution and was crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 74.62; H, 7.7. C₂₁H₂₄O₄ requires C, 74.12; H, 7.06%). It does not give any colouration with ferric chloride. The 2:4-*D.N.P.* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 240° (Found: N, 16.2. C₃₃H₃₂N₈O₁₀ requires N, 16%).

The structure of the above diketone is confirmed thus:

On methylation of the diketone with dimethyl sulphate and alkali 1,9-bis(*p*-methoxy phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione was obtained which is identical with the diketone obtained from anisole and azeloyl chloride. *p*-Anisic acid is obtained by oxidation of the methoxy diketone with alkaline KMnO₄.

The compounds prepared with other phenols and phenolic ethers following the above procedure are described in Table I. The compounds prepared with sebasoyl chloride are described in Table II.

TABLE I
Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic ethers with Azeloyl chloride

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found :	Reqd.:	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
Anisole	1,9-bis (<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione. Prismatic rods (alcohol), m.p. 99°.	(I, R ₂ =OMe R=R ₁ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H n = 7) C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄	C, 74.9 H, 7.60	C, 75.00 H, 7.61	m.p. 130° (yellow needles) (Found : N, 15.52; C ₃₅ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₀ requires N, 15.38%).	On oxidation gives <i>p</i> -anisic acid; m.p. 184°.
<i>o</i> -cresol	1,9-bis (3-methyl-4 hydroxy phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione, crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 139°.	(I, R ₂ =OH R ₃ =CH ₃ R=R ₁ =R ₄ =H, n = 7) C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄	C, 74.6 H, 7.20	C, 75.00 H, 7.61	Yellow needles m.p. 210° (Found : N, 15.42. C ₃₅ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₀ requires N, 15.38%).	No colouration with ferric chloride. Methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether with azeloyl chloride.
<i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether.	1,9-bis (3 methyl-4-methoxy phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione. Prismatic rods (dilute alcohol), m.p. 140°.	(I, R ₂ =OMe, R ₃ =CH ₃ R=R ₁ =R ₄ =H, n=7) C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₄	C, 75.66 H, 8.00	C, 75.76 H, 8.08	m.p. 200° (Found : N, 14.20; C ₃₇ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₁₀ requires N, 14.81%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ . Oxidation by alkaline KMnO ₄ gives 4-methoxy- <i>isophthalic</i> acid, m.p. 274° (mixed m.p.).
<i>m</i> -cresol	1,9-bis (<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione. Crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 100°.	(I, R ₂ =OH, R ₄ =CH ₃ , R=R ₁ =R ₃ =H, n=7) C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄	C, 74.9 H, 7.50	C, 75.00 H, 7.61	m.p. 250° (Found : N, 15.68; C ₃₅ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₀ requires N, 15.38%).	On methylation gives 1,9-bis (2-methyl-4-methoxy-phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione, m.p. 120°. On oxidation it gives 4-methoxy phthalic acid m.p. 168° (mixed m.p.).

TABLE I—(Continued)

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found :	Reqd.:	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
<i>p</i> -cresol	(a) 1,9-bis (<i>o</i> -hydroxy- <i>p</i> -tolyl phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione. Crystallised from dilute ethanol as rectangular plates, m.p. 71°.	(I, R=R ₂ =R ₃ =H, R ₁ =CH ₃ , R ₄ =OH, <i>n</i> = 7) C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄ .	C, 75.2 H, 7.41	C, 75.00 H, 7.61	m.p. 84° (Found : N, 15.50. C ₃₅ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀ requires N, 15.38%).	
	(b) 7-(<i>o</i> -hydroxy- <i>p</i> -tolyl benzoyl) octoic acid. Crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 80°.	(II, R=R ₂ =R ₃ =H, R ₁ =CH ₃ , R ₄ =OH, <i>n</i> = 7). C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ .	C, 69.00 H, 7.7	C, 69.06 H, 7.91	m.p. 110°; yellow needles. (Found : N, 12.46. C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₇ requires N, 12.23%).	
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	7-(<i>o</i> -hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl) octoic acid. Crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 85°.	(II, R=R ₂ =R ₃ =H, R ₁ =Cl, R ₄ =OH, <i>n</i> = 7). C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl.	C, 60.90 H, 6.24	C, 60.30 H, 6.37	m.p. 150° (Found : N, 11.96; C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₄ Cl requires N, 11.70%).	
<i>p</i> -chloro- <i>m</i> -cresol.	1,9-bis (2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4-methyl phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione or 1,9-bis (2-hydroxy-5-chloro-6-methyl phenyl) nonane-1,9-dione, crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 105°.	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₄ Cl ₂	C, 63.00 H, 5.70	C, 63.16 H, 5.95	m.p. 200° (Found: N, 14.32. C ₃₅ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₁₀ Cl ₂ requires N, 14.05%).	

TABLE II

Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic ethers with Sebasoyl chloride

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found :	Reqd.:	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
Phenol	(a) 8-(<i>p</i> -hydroxy benzoyl) nonanoic acid, colourless needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 114°.	(II, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H, R ₂ = OH, n = 8) C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ .	C, 68.85 H, 8.10	C, 69.06 H, 7.91	m.p. 160° (Found : N, 12.98; C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 12.23%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ . On methylation gives a product identical with the keto acid obtained from anisole and sebasoyl chloride. On oxidation it gives <i>p</i> -anisic acid, m.p. 184° (mixed m.p.).
	(b) 1,10-bis (<i>p</i> -hydroxy phenyl) decane-1,10-dione. Crystallised from ethanol as prismatic rods, m.p. 197°.	(I, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H, R ₂ = OH, n = 8) C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ .	C, 74.65 H, 7.87	C, 74.57 H, 7.34	m.p. 224° (Found: N, 16.00; C ₃₄ H ₄₄ N ₈ O ₁₀ requires N, 15.69%).	On methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from anisole and sebasoyl chloride. On oxidation it gives <i>p</i> -anisic acid, m.p. 184° (mixed m.p.).
Anisole	(a) 8-(<i>p</i> -methoxy benzoyl) nonanoic acid, crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 130°.	(II, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H, R ₂ = OCH ₃ , n = 8) C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ .	C, 69.61 H, 8.11	C, 69.86 H, 8.21	m.p. 79° (Found: N, 12.10; C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 11.86%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ .
	(b) 1,10 bis (<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl) decane 1,10 dione. Prismatic rods from alcohol m.p. 130°.	(I, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H, R ₂ = OCH ₃ , n = 8) C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄ .	C, 75.16 H, 8.20	C, 75.39 H, 7.85	m.p. 142°, needles, m.p. 142° (Found: N, 15.00; C ₂₆ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₁₀ requires N, 15.09%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ .
<i>o</i> -cresol.	(a) 8-(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>m</i> -toluyl) nonanoic acid, crystallised from dilute ethanol as prismatic rods, m.p. 83°.	(II, R = R ₁ = R ₄ = H, R ₂ = OH, R ₃ = CH ₃ , n = 8) C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ .	C, 69.51 H, 8.32	C, 69.86 H, 8.21	Yellow needles m.p. 105° (Found : N, 12.10; C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 11.86%).	Methylation gives 8-(<i>p</i> -methoxy- <i>m</i> -toluyl) nonanoic acid, m.p. 100°. On oxidation gives 4-methoxy isophthalic acid, m.p. 273° (mixed m.p.).
	(b) 1, 10 bis (3-methyl-4-hydroxy phenyl) decane 1,10 dione. Prismatic rods from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 196°.	(I, R = R ₁ = R ₄ = H, R ₂ = OH, R ₃ = CH ₃ , n = 8) C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄ .	C, 75.27 H, 7.84	C, 75.39 H, 7.85	Yellow prisms, m.p. 152° (Found : N, 15.0; C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N 15.09%).	On methylation it gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether and sebasoyl chloride. On oxidation it gives 4-methoxy isophthalic acid, m.p. 275° (mixed m.p.).

TABLE II—(Continued)

Phenols and phenolic ethers	Product formed	Formula	Found :	Reqd. :	Derivative (2 : 4-D.N.P.)	Remarks
<i>o</i> -cresol-methyl ether.	1,10 bis (3-methyl-4-methoxy phenyl) decane dione, crystallised from dilute alcohol as prismatic rods, m.p. 131°.	(I, R = R ₁ = R ₄ = H R ₂ = OMe, R ₃ = CH ₃ , n = 8). C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₄	C, 76.11 H, 8.45	C, 76.10 H, 8.29	m.p. 207° (Found: N, 14.26; C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 14.54%).	No colouration with FeCl ₃ .
<i>m</i> -cresol	1,10 bis (<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -toluyl phenyl) decane dione. Crystallised from ethanol as needles.	(I, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H R ₂ = OH, R ₄ = CH ₃ , n = 8) C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄	C, 75.00 H, 7.80	C, 75.39 H, 7.85	m.p. 190° (Found N, 15.20; C ₂₆ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 15.09%).	On methylation gives 1,10-bis (2-methyl-4-methoxy phenyl) decane-1,10-dione, identical with the dike-tone obtained from <i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether and sebasoyl chloride, which on oxidation gives 4-methoxy phthalic acid, m.p. 169° (mixed m.p.).
<i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether.	1,10 bis (2-methyl-4-methoxy phenyl) decane dione. Crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 110°.	(I, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H. R ₂ = OMe, R ₄ = CH ₃ , n = 8). C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₄	C, 76.53 H, 8.64	C, 76.10 H, 8.29	m.p. 150° (Found N, 14.68; C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 14.54%).	
<i>p</i> -Chloro-Phenol	8-(<i>o</i> -hydroxy-5-chloro benzoyl) nonanoic acid, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 134°.	(II, R = R ₂ = R ₃ = H, R ₁ = Cl, R ₄ = OH, n = 8). C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ Cl	C, 61.44 H, 6.72	C, 61.44 H, 6.72	m.p. 198° (Found: N, 11.00. C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₄ Cl requires N, 11.37%).	
<i>p</i> -cresol	1,10 bis (<i>o</i> -hydroxy-5-toluyl phenyl) decane-1,10-dione. Rectangular plates from alcohol, m.p. 126°.	(I, R = R ₂ = R ₃ = H, R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₄ = OH, n = 8). C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₄	C, 75.20 H, 7.84	C, 75.39 H, 7.85	m.p. 200° (Found : N, 15.46. C ₂₆ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₈ requires N, 15.09%).	Colouration with FeCl ₃ .
2-chloro-5-hydroxy toluene.	1,10-bis(2-hydroxy-5-chloro-6-methyl phenyl) decane-1,10-dione, or, 1,10-bis (2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5 chloro-phenyl) decane-1,10-dione. Needles from alcohol.	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ Cl ₂	C, 63.96 H, 6.80	C, 63.86 H, 6.21	m.p. 193° (Found : N, 13.00. C ₂₆ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₈ Cl ₂ requires N, 13.81%).	

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Received January 13, 1969